

Synthesis and Studies of some Substituted Phthalides

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A number of substituted phthalides obtained by condensation of phenols with *o*-phthalaldehydic and 3 : 4-dimethoxy-*o*-phthalaldehydic (ψ -opianic acid) acids are described. The constitution of the dyes has been studied and the visible UV and IR spectra have been presented. The absorption maxima of the dyes have been found to be like those of phthalins.

PHTHALIDES from phthalaldehydic acid are of great utility, thus, phthalides¹ obtained from phthalaldehydic acid and different amides are useful for the control of nematodes and insects; phthalides² obtained from phthalaldehydic acid and different aromatic amines are useful as herbicides and for the growth and germination of seeds; mono- and polyphthalidyl ethers³ prepared by esterification of polyalcohols with phthalaldehydic acid, have antimicrobial properties.

The *o*-phthalaldehydic (I; R'₁ = R'₂ = R'₃ = R'₄ = H) and 3 : 4-dimethoxy-*o*-phthalaldehydic (I; R'₁ = R'₂ = H and R'₃ = R'₄ = OCH₃) acids have been found to cyclise to their lactol forms (II), which yield well crystalline acetyl derivatives (III) retaining their cyclic structures. The pseudo esters as well as large number of all other alkyl derivatives^{4,5} obtained through lactol intermediate and n.m.r. spectra of phthalaldehydic acid⁶ confirm the formation of cyclic isomers. The cyclic derivatives⁷⁻⁹, pseudo chlorides and pseudo esters are obtained through lactol intermediate. IR^{10,11}, Raman spectra¹² and n.m.r.¹³ have further confirmed the formation of cyclic isomers.

Results and Discussion

Bistrzycki¹⁴ was the first to prepare some substituted phthalides from *o*-phthalaldehydic acid by condensation with phenols, and also reported the condensation product of opianic acid with phenol. Later these reactions were re-examined by Brubaker and Adams¹⁵ by condensing opianic and *o*-phthalaldehydic acids with phenol and other aromatic hydroxy compounds.

In the present work the 3-substituted phthalides have been prepared by the condensation of *o*-phthalaldehydic and ψ -opianic acids with other various aromatic hydroxy compounds, and the present work records the chemical and spectral studies of the resulting dyes. In some of the common cases (phenol dyes) the starting materials are the same as employed by the previous workers¹⁵ but the reaction conditions are quite different; in the present work

the melting points of the phenol dyes are higher than those reported.¹⁵

The condensation with phenols follows through the equilibrium process of lactol form (II) of the acids (I) and with excess of phenol the entire acid taken reacts as lactol. In case of phenol the condensation may take place at ortho¹⁶ or para-position¹⁴ or at both positions¹⁵. Owing to small amount of the compound this has not been proved. Moreover, if isomeric impurities are present the separation by crystallization are frequently rendered difficult due to the formation of gums. The purity of the dyes (IVa; R'₁ = R'₂ = R'₃ = R'₄ = H; R'₁ = R'₂ = H and R'₃ = R'₄ = OCH₃) has been confirmed by paper chromatography. The structure has been confirmed by chemical and i.r. studies (3300 cm⁻¹, OH and 1770 cm⁻¹, γ -lactone). Potassium hydroxide fusion of the dyes (IVb) produced (V; R'₁ = R'₂ = R'₃ = R'₄ = H; R'₁ = R'₂ = H and R'₃ = R'₄ = OCH₃) and resorcinol (VI). The diacetyl derivatives (IVg) and dibromo derivatives (IVh) support the presence of resorcinol moiety in the dyes (IVb). The compounds (IVa-IVh) possess γ -lactone (1770 cm⁻¹). The peak at 3300 cm⁻¹ (OH) in (IVb) is found to be absent in (IVg) and new peaks at 1200 and 1125 cm⁻¹ (phenolic acetate) appear.

The absorption maxima (λ_{max}) of 3-substituted phthalides (IV) given in Table 2 have been found comparable to those of true phthalins.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The absorption maxima (UV and visible) have been recorded using model DU Beckman Spectrophotometer in absolute ethanol (neutral and alkaline media) and IR were determined from KBr using a Perkin Elmer infracond.

The phenols (phenol, resorcinol, catechol, hydroquinone, phloroglucinol and pyrogallol) have been taken in slight excess of molecular proportion than the acids (I). Concentrated H₂SO₄ (4-6 drops) has been used as condensing agent throughout and each dye, when tested, is found free from sulphur.

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TABLE 1. PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF 3-PHENYLPHTHALIDES (IV; $R_1' = R_2' = R_3' = R_4' = H$) AND 3-PHENYL-4,5-DIMETHOXYPHTHALIDES (IV; $R_1' = R_2' = H$ AND $R_3' = R_4' = OCH_3$) RESPECTIVELY

Dyes	3-() phthalide and 3-() 4,5-dimethoxyphthalide	Condensation			Appearance (micro- crystalline)	Calcd. %		Found %	
		Temp. °C	Dura- tion hr	m.p. °C		C	H	C	H
IVa*	(<i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl)	115°-20°	6	210°-12°	Light brown	74.33,	4.42	74.50,	4.54
IVc	(2',3'-dihydroxyphenyl)	100°	5	> 300°	Blackish brown	69.42,	4.13	69.60,	4.37
IVd	(2',5'-dihydroxyphenyl)	100°	4.30	> 300°	Brownish black	69.42,	4.13	69.59,	4.38
IVe	(2',4',6'-trihydroxyphenyl)	115°	5	> 300°	Light orange	65.12,	3.87	64.90,	4.11
IVf	(2',3',4'-trihydroxyphenyl)	115°-20°	4.30	> 300°	Brownish black	65.12,	3.87	64.89,	4.10
IVg	(2',4'-diacetylphenyl)	130°-40°	4	215°-16°	Colourless	66.26,	4.29	66.10,	4.45
IVh	(2',4'-dihydroxy-3',5'-dibromophenyl)	room	over- night	> 300°	Brick red	(Acetyl, 26.28) Br, 39.97		(Acetyl, 26.26) Br, 39.91	
IVa*	(2' or 4'-hydroxyphenyl)	110°-15°	9	248°-50°	Light brown	67.13,	4.89	67.00,	4.80
IVb	(2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl)	110°-20°	1.30	> 300°	Chocolate brown	63.67,	4.63	63.30,	4.84
IVc	(2',3'-dihydroxyphenyl)	110°-20°	2.30	> 300°	Dark brown	63.57,	4.63	63.34,	4.84
IVd	(2',5'-dihydroxyphenyl)	120°-30°	2.30	190°	Light brown	63.57,	4.63	63.32,	4.85
IVe	(2',4',6'-trihydroxyphenyl)	120°-30°	1.30	> 300°	Chocolate brown	60.38,	4.40	60.16,	4.25
IVf	(2',3',4'-trihydroxyphenyl)	100°-15°	3.30	> 300°	Brown	60.38,	4.40	60.18,	4.30
IVg	(2',4'-diacetylphenyl)	130°-40°	4	165°	Light yellow	(Acetyl, 22.25) Br, 34.75	4.66	(Acetyl, 22.28) Br, 34.69	4.54
IVh	(2',4'-dihydroxy-3',5'-dibromophenyl)	room	over- night	> 300°	Brick red				

* Excess phenol, after condensation was removed by steam distillation.

TABLE 2. ABSORPTION MAXIMA (NM) OF 3-PHENYL PHTHALIDES (IV; $R_1' = R_2' = R_3' = R_4' = H$) AND 3-PHENYL-4,5-DIMETHOXYPHTHALIDES (IV; $R_1' = R_2' = H$ AND $R_3' = R_4' = OCH_3$) RESPECTIVELY. G.F. = GREEN FLUORESCENCE.

Dyes	Colour in Ethanol		Col. with 2% NaOH	EtOH λ_{max}	EtOH-NaOH λ_{max} pH	
	Neutral	Alkaline				
IVa	reddish pink	light pink	dark reddish pink	500 & 530	500 & 530;	8.5
IVb	yellow-red (G.F.)	reddish pink (G.F.)	reddish pink (G.F.)	460	500	; 9.0
IVc	yellow-red	red	reddish pink	470 & 490	460 & 500;	8.8
IVd	green	brownish, yellow	brownish-yellow	450, 625 & 700	450	; 8.9
IVe	yellow red	reddish pink	pinkish red	400 & 500	500	; 9.8
IVf	yellow brown	yellow-brown	brownish red
IVg	pale-yellow	pale-yellow	pale yellow	340
IVh	pinkish orange (G.F.)	intensified pink-orange	dark pink	530	530	; 9.5
IVa	light-red (pink tinge)	pinkish-violet	pinkish violet	480 & 515	565	; 9.0
IVb	yellow-red (G.F.)	reddish pink (G.F.)	reddish pink (G.F.)	470 & 500	510	; 8.8
IVc	yellow-brown	green	green	445	610 & 650;	8.9
IVd	light green	light brown	brownish red	600 & 650	460	; 8.9
IVe	reddish yellow	yellow-red	bright red	420 & 450	480	; 9.8
IVf	yellow-brown	dark brown	brownish red	390
IVg	pale-yellow	pale yellow	pale yellow	335
IVh	reddish pink (G.F.)	pink (G.F.)	dark pink	540	540	; 9.8

3-(2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl) phthalide (IVb; $R_1' = R_2' = R_3' = R_4' = H$):

A mixture of 9.0 g acid (I) and 9.0 g resorcinol was heated in an oil bath to 86°. Few drops (8-10) of concentrated H_2SO_4 were added to the homogeneous contents, and after heating for 4 hr at 100° a hard and brittle mass was obtained. The condensed mass was crushed and washed with water to remove excess of resorcinol. It was extracted with 2% aqueous sodium hydroxide and the dye stuff was

precipitated from pinkish red (green fluorescent) filtrate by gradual addition of dilute HCl with constant stirring. The dye was purified by repeated crystallisation from rectified spirit, dried in an oven at 110° and then in a vacuum desiccator (Yield 9.1 g).

The orange yellow dye, m.p. > 300°, is micro-crystalline. The ethanolic solution is yellowish red with green fluorescence which on addition of alkali gives red colour with intensified green fluorescence.

- IVa, $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{R}_4 = \text{R}_5 = \text{H}; \text{R}_3 = \text{OH}$
 IVb, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_4 = \text{R}_5 = \text{H}; \text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{OH}$
 IVc, $\text{R}_3 = \text{R}_4 = \text{R}_5 = \text{H}; \text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{OH}$
 IVd, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{R}_5 = \text{H}; \text{R}_1 = \text{R}_4 = \text{OH}$
 IVe, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}; \text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{R}_5 = \text{OH}$
 IVf, $\text{R}_4 = \text{R}_5 = \text{H}; \text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{OH}$
 IVg, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_4 = \text{R}_5 = \text{H}; \text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{O.COCH}_3$
 IVh, $\text{R}_5 = \text{H}; \text{R}_2 = \text{R}_4 = \text{Br}; \text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{OH}$
 Or
 $(\text{R}'_1 = \text{R}'_2 = \text{R}'_3 = \text{R}'_4 = \text{H})$
 $(\text{R}'_1 = \text{R}'_2 = \text{H}; \text{R}'_3 = \text{R}'_4 = \text{OCH}_3)$

$(\text{R}'_1 = \text{R}'_2 = \text{R}'_3 = \text{R}'_4 = \text{H} \quad \text{Or} \quad \text{R}'_1 = \text{R}'_2 = \text{H}; \text{R}'_3 = \text{R}'_4 = \text{OCH}_3)$

Anal. Calcd for $C_{14}H_{10}O_4$: C, 69.42; H, 4.13, M. wt., 242.

Found : C, 69.42; H, 4.36; M. wt., 232 (Rast).

The preparation of rest of the dyes given in Table I has been done in identical manner as already described.

Chromatography of dyes (IVa) : On test paper—Whatman No. I, *n*-butanol-ammonia was allowed to run for 13 hr (descending) to give two corresponding pink spots of the dyes (IVa; $R'_1 = R'_2 = R'_3 = R'_4 = H$; $R'_1 = R'_2 = H$ and $R'_3 = R'_4 = OCH_3$) showing the purity of the compounds.

Acetylation of dyes (IVb) : Each dye 1 g. acetic anhydride 15 ml and fused sodium acetate 2 g were refluxed at $130^\circ-40^\circ$ for 4 hr to give colourless (IVg; $R'_1 = R'_2 = R'_3 = R'_4 = H$) (1 g), m.p. $215^\circ-16^\circ$ and faint yellow (IVg; $R'_1 = R'_2 = H$ and $R'_3 = R'_4 = OCH_3$) (0.92 g), m.p. 165° as microcrystalline compounds (from rectified spirit) which are soluble in ethanol, acetone and acetic acid.

Anal. Calcd for $C_{18}H_{14}O_6$ or $C_{14}H_8O_4(COCH_3)_2$ ($R'_1 = R'_2 = R'_3 = R'_4 = H$)
Acetyl, 26.28; C, 66.26; H, 4.29.

Found : Acetyl, 26.26; C, 66.10; H, 4.45

Anal. Calcd for $C_{20}H_{18}O_8$ or $C_{16}H_{12}O_6(COCH_3)_2$ ($R'_1 = R'_2 = H$ and $R'_3 = R'_4 = OCH_3$)
Acetyl, 22.28; C, 62.17; H, 4.66.

Found : Acetyl, 22.25; C, 62.00; H, 4.54.

Bromination of dyes (IVb) : Each dye (IVb) (1 g) was dissolved in minimum quantity of ethanol; 2 ml of bromine (excess) was added to it gradually with constant shaking. The contents left overnight at room temperature gave brick red dibromo compounds (IVh; $R'_1 = R'_2 = R'_3 = R'_4 = H$) (0.99 g), m.p. > 300 and (IVh; $R'_1 = R'_2 = H$ and $R'_3 = R'_4 = OCH_3$) (0.98 g), m.p. > 300 (from rectified spirit). The dibromo-compounds dissolve in ethanol with pinkish orange colour and light green fluorescence and intensified on addition of dilute NaOH to pink colour with yellow green fluorescence.

Anal. Calcd for $C_{14}H_8O_4Br_2$ ($R'_1 = R'_2 = R'_3 = R'_4 = H$)

Br; 39.97; Found : Br, 39.91

Anal. Calcd for $C_{16}H_{12}O_6Br_2$ ($R'_1 = R'_2 = H$ and $R'_3 = R'_4 = OCH_3$)

Br; 34.75; Found : Br, 34.69.

Caustic potash fusion of dyes (IVb) : Each dye (1 g) and a paste of KOH pellets (10 g) taken in a platinum crucible were heated at 300° on a sand bath for 4 hr until the pink colour of the dye faded completely. The contents were diluted with 50 ml

of distilled water, filtered and excess of alkali was neutralized giving a light pink residue (A). The filtrate was further acidified by adding an excess of dilute HCl giving a light yellow residue (B); it was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from hot water and ethanol. The filtrate was shaken with ether and on evaporation of excess solvent a brownish red residue (C) was obtained.

Residue (A) was identified as unreacted residual dye (IVb; $R'_1 = R'_2 = R'_3 = R'_4 = H$) and (IVb; $R'_1 = R'_2 = H$; $R'_3 = R'_4 = OCH_3$) giving all colour reactions of the dye itself and was further confirmed by mixed melting point determination. Residue (B) was identified as acid (V; $R'_1 = R'_2 = R'_3 = R'_4 = H$) and (V; $R'_1 = R'_2 = H$; $R'_3 = R'_4 = OCH_3$) and confirmed by m.p., mixed m.p. and superimposition of i.r. spectra with the authentic samples. Residue (C) was identified as resorcinol (VI); in each case it responded to ferric chloride, ammoniacal silver nitrate and Fehling's solution test. It was further confirmed by m.p. and mixed m.p. determination.

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